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Influence Of Peer Pressure On Students’ Behavioural Patterns And Academic Achievement In Universities In North Central Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the Influence of Peer Pressure on Students’ Behavioural Patterns and Academic Achievement in the Universities in North-central Nigeria. four objectives, four research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The research design were descriptive survey and ex-post facto. The population of the study was 25,115 students and 394 were randomly sampled using 5% of Yamane table of sample size (1967). The instrument used was a self-structured questionnaire titled: ‘Peer Pressure Questionnaire’ (PPQ). The instrument was validated through expert assessment. The instrument was pilot tested and the results of the two administrations were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMCC) which yielded a reliability index of 0.76 and was considered reliable for the study. The copies of the instrument were administered and 394 were sieved based on code. The collected data were analyzed using frequency counts and percentages for demographic data. While mean scores and standard deviation were used to answers the research questions. The hypotheses 1 to 2 were tested using t-test. While hypothesis 3 was tested using ANOVA. Findings revealed that, peer pressure influenced behavioural patterns of students negatively such as cultism, cheating, and indecent dressing. It was also revealed that students academic achievement were within average. Results from the tested hypotheses revealed that Federal and State Universities students did not differ significantly in the influence of peer pressure as regards to secret cult and clubbing. It was found that students’ academic achievement were withi average irrespective of gender while male students were more victims of negative of peer pressure. It was, therefore, recommended among others, that Guidance counsellors, parents, teachers, religious bodies and other stakeholders should organize gender based programme both at the Federal and State Universities to discuss the influence of negative peer pressure in relation to students’ behavioural patterns and academic achievement in the Universities.

Keywords: academic achievement, behavioural patterns, students

INTRODUCTION

In educational setting, the interplay between peer pressure and students’ behavioural patterns as well as academic achievement has garnered significant attention among educators, parents and other stakeholders. This setting amplifies the effects of peer pressure, which can be both positive and negative. On one hand, students may be encouraged by peers to engage in productive academic behaviours, such as studying collaboratively or participating in study groups. On the other hand, they may also face negative

influences that may lead to procrastination, substance abuse, clubbing or disengagement from academic responsibilities due to negative influences.

However, peer pressure refers to direct and indirect influence on people of age grade or members of social groups with similar interests, experience and social status. More so, members of a peer group are more likely to influence a person's beliefs and behaviour (Adeagbo, 2013). In addition, peer pressure may affect individuals of all ethnicities, genders and ages, because it offers opportunities for students and adults alike to instil or experience pressure every day (Mason, Dyer & Michael 2019). Peer pressure on the similar note is the influence that peers can have on each other which could be positive or negative.

In other words, it is the emotional or mental forces from people belonging to the same group (such as age, grade or status) to act or behave in the same manner (Ademorokun, 2013). Many students may be confronted with several influences like birthday parties, clubs, indecent dressing, substance abuse, prostitution, and cultism which may ultimately affect their behavioural patterns and academic achievement negatively. Adetunji (2013) argue that peer pressure is linked to social demands because many students fall victim of negative social demands as a result of friends and the level of their economic status. Oludele (2021) opined that over-protected children as well as children from low economic status usually fall victim of negative peer pressure.

However, in our present-day society, students tend to disobey their parents and obey their friends or peers. They may sometimes, take directives from their friends in the school which often influences their behavioural patterns and academic achievement negatively. Adeola (2013), asserted that it is very essential for parents to watch out for the company their children associate with or keep in the school by visiting them occasionally. A popular adage once said, "show me your friend and I will tell you who you are". This means that if a student or a child associates with drug pushers or abusers, sooner or later, he/she will join the group.

It is also believed that, if a students associates with rogues and armed robbers, he may be persuaded to join the group on one of their trips and share in the booty, a trial will convince you! so they say (Gibson, 2019). Conclusively, parents may largely be responsible for the lapses in their children's behaviour. In addition, Ajibade (2016) stated that, parents are expected to serve as role-models and inculcate the right value in their children.

However, the pressure to conform to social construct and groups expectations some times took a toll on students' mental health which can result to worry, anxiety, frustration, irrational thoughts, depression and it may ultimately lead to suicide attempt due to misuse of opportunities and freedom. For this reason, many students may be confronted with academic setback or decline in grades.

The effect of all these pressure could force students to become armed robbers, thieves, kidnappers, hired assassins, thugs, scammers, fraudsters, and other forms of social vices which may contribute to many security challenges facing our present-day society, especially in North Central Nigeria. For these lapses in the lives of some students, society, and indeed parents, teachers and other adult members of the larger community have been in great pain and distress due to the seeming lack of good behaviour of the majority of students. It is against this background coupled with the researcher's experience of some destructive effects of peer influence on students' behavioural patterns and academic achievement as well as the society at large, that this study focused on investigating the influence of peer pressure on students' behavioural patterns and academic achievement in University in North Central Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The study was guided by the following objectives which were to:

- i. find out the influence of peer pressure on students' behavioural patterns in relation to cultism in the Universities in North-central Nigeria;
- ii. examine the level of academic achievement of students in the Universities in North-central Nigeria;
- iii. examine the influence of peer pressure on students' behavioural patterns in relation to clubbing in the Universities in North-central Nigeria.
- iv. investigate the influence of peer pressure on students' academic achievement in the Universities in North central, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The researchers raised the following questions which guided the study.

1. What is the influence of peer pressure on students' behavioural patterns in relation to cultism in the Universities in North-central Nigeria?
2. What is the level of academic achievement of students in the Universities in North-central Nigeria?
3. What is the influence of peer pressure on students' behavioural patterns in relation to clubbing in the Universities in North-central Nigeria?
4. What is the influence of peer pressure on students' academic achievement in the Universities in North central Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study and it was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H01: There is no significant difference between Federal and State Universities students on the influence of peer pressure and their behavioural patterns in relation to cultism in North-central Nigeria.

H02: There is no significant difference between males and female students on the influence of peer pressure and their behavioural patterns in relation to clubbing in the University in North-central Nigeria.

H03: Federal and state universities students did not differ significantly on the influence of peer pressure on their academic achievement in North Central Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive survey research design and ex-post facto. This survey research design involved collecting data from selected representatives of a population through research instrument and analyzing same to obtain results (Nworgu, 2016). On the other hand, ex-post facto is a type of non experimental study where the researcher analyzes existing data or condition after they have occurred.

Therefore, survey research design and ex-post facto method were ideal since the researchers were interested in subjecting the collected data to rigorous statistical analysis and hypotheses testing.

The population of this study was 25,115 which consist of all two hundred level students from three state universities and three Federal universities in North-central Nigeria.

The sample size for this study was 394 out of 25,115 students from six university which include both state and Federal Universities within the study area. This study adopted stratified random sampling technique in selecting the sample size from the population. The researchers considered the formula of Yamane (1967) as appropriate. Therefore, a total of 394 students were used as the respondents based on 5% of Yamane (1967). The instrument for this study was a self-structured questionnaire, titled Influence of Peer Pressure Questionnaire'' (PPQ). This instrument was divided into two sections, A and B. Section A consisted on demographic data of the respondents while section B consists on items on peer pressure. It had 17 items drawn on a 4-point scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1).

In order to establish the validity of the research instrument, the questionnaire was submitted to the two expert in the Department of Guidance and Counselling, Faculty of Education, University of Abuja for face, construct and content validity. After much corrections, constructive criticisms and observations on the content and the construct, it was therefore certified valid for the study.

The instrument was also subjected to a pilot test using 20 students of two hundred level (200) in University of Abuja. This was carried out in Faculty of Education, University of Abuja, that would not be part in the main study. The reliability of the instrument was determined using test-retest method. After two weeks of the first administration of the test, the test was re-administered to the same group of students and the results from the two administrations were correlated using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMCC). The result therefore, yielded the reliability index of 0.76 which was considered reliable for the study.

The researchers and research assistants took permission from the Head of sampled Universities' Departments through the letter of introduction from the Department of Guidance and Counselling,

University of Abuja. The researchers with the research assistants also applied for two hundred level students result particularly second semester result. The request was granted and for the purpose of identification, the result was coded along with the instrument using the last digit of students' registration number.

The respondents in this study was randomly picked from two departments and four programmes which are Educational Foundation and Science Education. This programme include Educational Psychology, Social Studies, Environmental Education and Biology Education. Thereafter, the researchers and research assistants administered 420 copies of the instrument to students in the lecture hall and 394 were sieved based on the code. More so, the researchers and the research assistants briefed the respondents on the intention of the questionnaire and appeal for cooperation as well as assuring them of utmost confidentiality. The respondents were told that the information given shall be used strictly for research work. In a situations where they did not understand some statement in the items, assistance were rendered by the researcher and research assistants by way of explaining the items on the questionnaire and allowing them to make their choices from the options provided.

Descriptive tool of frequency count and percentages were used to analyzed the demographic data while mean scores and standard deviation were used to answers the research questions. The testing of the hypotheses were done using inferential statistical tool of t-test. The hypotheses 1 to 2 were tested using a t-test because two groups were compared. While hypothesis 3 was tested One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to determine differences between more than two groups.

The decision rule was any statements that had 2.50 and above were considered as agreed while any statement below 2.50 was considered disagreed. The decision rule for all the hypotheses was that, any significant value that was 0.05 level of significance and above was accepted and any significance value that was below 0.05 level of significance was therefore rejected.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents based on Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	206	52.30
Female	188	47.70
Total	394	100.00

Table 1 showed the distribution of respondents based on gender. The number of male respondents was 206 (52.30%) while the female counterparts was 188 (47.70%). This means that there were more male genders in this study than female genders.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents based on Federal and State Universities

Federal/State	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Federal Universities	205	52.00
State Universities	189	48.00
Total	394	100.00

Table 2 showed the distribution of respondents based on Federal and State University. The number of Federal Universities respondents was 205 (52.00%) while the State Universities counterparts was 189 (48.00%). This means that there were more respondents from Federal Universities than respondents from State Universities.

Research Question One: *What is the influence of peer pressure on students' behavioural patterns in relation to cultism in North-central, Nigeria?*

Table 3: Influence of peer pressure on students' behavioural patterns in relation to cultism in North-central, Nigeria

N=394				
S/N	Statements	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
3.	Friends lured me into cult group.	3.10	.845	Agreed
4.	Fear of intimidation make me join secret cult which has ruined my life.	3.12	.750	Agreed
5.	Friends deceived me into secret cult in the name of power.	3.15	.660	Agreed
6.	Desire for freedom make me join secret cult through my friends.	3.14	.834	Agreed
7.	I was not told the implication until I join the secret cult.	3.00	.823	Agreed
8.	The greatest mistake I ever made is to join secret cult because my friends insisted.	2.86	1.031	Agreed
Sectional Mean		3.62	0.824	

Table 3 showed the influence of peer pressure on students' behavioural patterns in relation to cultism in North-central Nigeria. The results indicated that the students agreed in all the items, that they were lured into cult group unconsciously, while others agreed that they join cult group as a result of intimidation and desire for power. The sectional mean score of respondents on the influence of peer pressure on students' behavioural pattern is 3.62, with a standard deviation of 0.824. This implies that the respondents agreed that friends lead them to secret cult as well as the desire for power in the Universities in North-central Nigeria. While result from standard deviation validated the findings.

Research Question Two: *What is the academic achievement of students in Universities in North-central Nigeria?*

Table 4: The academic achievement of students in Universities in North-central Nigeria

N=394			
	Minimum	Maximum	Average Score
EDU202	15.00	79.00	48.05
EDU206	14.00	67.00	46.23
GST202	17.00	72.00	47.10
GST222	40.00	88.00	64.52
Academic Achievement	30.50	66.25	51.26

Table 4 showed the academic achievement of students in Universities in North central Nigeria. The minimum score in EDU 202 was 15.00, while the maximum score was 79.00 with the average score of 48.05. This means that the students score in EDU 202 was below average. The students score in EDU 206 has a minimum of 14.00, a maximum of 67.00 and an average score of 46.23. This also shows that the students score in EDU 206 was below average.

The minimum students score in GST 202 is 17.00, the maximum score 72.00 with average score of 47.10. This means that the students score in GST 211 was below average. The minimum students score in GST 222 was 40.00, the maximum score 88.00 with average score of 64.52. This means that the students score in GST 222 was above average.

The academic achievement of students in Universities in North central Nigeria is minimum of 30.50, maximum of 66.25 and average of 51.26. The average score of 51.26 is within 50 midpoint which implies

that overall academic performance of students was within average. To further answer the research questions, hypotheses were tested.

Research Question Three: *What is the influence of peer pressure on students' behavioural patterns in relation to clubbing in Universities in North-central, Nigeria?*

Table 5: Influence of peer pressure on students' behavioural patterns in relation to clubbing in Universities in North-central, Nigeria

N=394

S/N	Statements	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
9.	I am addicted to clubbing through my friends	3.20	.882	Agreed
10.	Clubs contributed to my misbehaviour.	3.37	.713	Agreed
11.	I can't do without attending a club per week	3.16	.755	Agreed
12.	I can miss test or exam because of club	2.83	1.083	Agreed
13.	I started going to club right from my hundred level	3.31	.660	Agreed
14.	I always waste my precious time in the club	3.18	.753	Agreed
15.	Pressure from my friends make me love clubs	3.02	.770	Agreed
16.	Night party make one to be socialized	2.64	1.004	Agreed
17.	Clubbing has ruined my life through my friends	3.26	.730	Agreed
Sectional Mean		3.11	0.817	

Table 5 showed the influence of peer pressure on students' behavioural patterns in relation to clubbing in Universities in North-central, Nigeria. The results in table showed that the students agreed with all the items, that they were addicted and became lovers of clubbing through friends. The sectional mean score of respondents for peer pressure in relation to clubbing is 3.11, with a standard deviation of 0.817. This implies that the peer pressure influence students' behavioural patterns in relation to clubbing negatively in Universities in North-central, Nigeria. The result from standard deviate indicate the phenomenological tendency of this social problems.

H01: There is no significant different between Federal and State Universities students on the influence of peer pressure and their behavioural patterns in relation to cultism in North-central, Nigeria.

Table 6: t-test on Difference between Federal and State Universities students on the influence of peer pressure and their behavioural patterns in relation to cultism in North-central, Nigeria

Location	Number	Mean	S.D.	t-value	df	Sig(2-tailed)	Decision
Federal Universities	280	3.07	.393	.795	392	.427	Accepted
State Univer.	114	3.04	.422				

Table 6 showed the significant different between Federal and State Universities students on the influence of peer pressure and their behavioural patterns in relation to cultism in North-central, Nigeria. With the significant values of .427 (more than the 0.05 level of significance), the hypothesis that says that there is no different between Federal and State Universities students on the influence of peer pressure and their behavioural patterns in relation to cultism in North-central Nigeria was, therefore accepted and conclude that Federal and State Universities respondents did not differ significantly in the influence of peer pressure on their behavioural patterns in relation to cultism in North-central, Nigeria, that both Federal and State Universities students belong to one cult group or the other.

H02: There is no significant difference between males and female students on the influence of peer pressure on their behavioural patterns in relation to clubbing in University in North-central, Nigeria.

Table 7: t-test on Difference between males and female students on the influence of peer pressure on their behavioural patterns in relation to clubbing in Universities in North-central, Nigeria.

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	t-value	df	Sig(2-tailed)	Decision
Male	206	3.13	.401	3.466	392	.001	Rejected
Female	188	2.99	.391				

Table 7 showed the significant difference between males and female students on the influence of peer pressure on their behavioural patterns in relation to clubbing in Universities in North-central, Nigeria. With the significant values of .001 (less than the 0.05 level of significance), the hypothesis that says that there is no significant difference between male and female students on the influence of peer pressure on their behavioural patterns in relation to clubbing in University in North-central, Nigeria was, therefore rejected and conclude that male and female respondents differ significantly in the influence of peer pressure on their behavioural patterns in relation to clubbing in University in North-central, Nigeria, that male students were more victims.

H03: Federal and state universities students did not differ significantly on the influence of peer pressure on their academic achievement in North Central Nigeria.

Table 8: One-way ANOVA for the difference between Federal and state universities students on the influence of peer pressure on their academic achievement in North Central Nigeria

FEDERAL AND STATE	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	.459	2	.039	.234	.641	Not Significant
Within Groups	48.895	391	.125			
Total	47.654	393				

The analysis in Table 8 was carried out to test the difference between Federal and state universities students on the influence of peer pressure on their academic achievement in North Central Nigeria. With the significant values of 0.641 (more than the 0.05 level of significance), the hypothesis that says that Federal and state universities students did not differ significantly on the influence of peer pressure on their academic achievement in North Central Nigeria is therefore, accepted and concluded that Federal and state universities students did not differ significantly on the influence of peer pressure on their academic achievement in North Central Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

It was also found from research question one that, there is bad behavioural patterns as a result of peers pressure among students in Universities in North-central Nigeria such as secret cult. One of the places where people learn and adapt to a certain condition is group formation. This group are usually people of the same social status, age and class which has the capacity to alter one's believe system into a negative one. For this reason, many individual choose to belong to one negative social group or the other like secret cult. Therefore, this finding is inline with the finding of Ajibade (2016), who discovered that, certain factors like the students' age range, socio-economic status and acceptance of cult group are the determinant of membership in most group. In like manner, the findings is also inline with the findings of Omollo and Yambo (2017), that peer pressure influenced students into cult group and contributed to many school drop out especially male students. In addition, this finding is also similar to the finding of Abdullahi (2018) that, factors like cultism, clubbing, and birthday party pressurized students most often in the learning environment. However, negative peer pressure are associated with negative behavioural patterns like secret cult and other maladaptive behaviour.

It was found from research question two that, the academic achievement of students in Universities in North-central Nigeria is within average. There is no doubt that, students who are suppose to be first class grade could drop down as a result of many circumstances like personal traits, and peer pressure. This findings is similar to the finding of Ajibade (2016) who found that, peer group influences the academic performance of students averagely. In like manner, the findings is also in line with the opinion of Chebet, (2018), who asserted that peer group members who perform averagely had positive influence on their academic performance in secondary schools. It was therefore concluded that, students' academic performance were average despite peer group influence. Therefore, some students who were suppose to be first class students end up becoming an average students due to influence of negative peer pressure. This similarities could be as a results of a common phenomenon as regards to students' academic achievement.

It was also found in research question three, that students were addicted to clubbing as a result of peer pressure in Universities in North central Nigeria. There are common saying that, 'show me your friend and I will tell you who you are. This saying simply refer that, you can't be different from your friend. This finding is inline with the thought of Fadere, Zarma, Fadere, Bademosi and Amanum (2021) who asserted that, negative peer group influence students' behaviour in relation to clubbing which lower one's academic performance irrespective of the institutions. The finding is also inline with the observation of Gebresilase and Zhao (2023), they found that, peer pressure had a mediating function especially in the area of addiction like clubbing, cultism and other negative social influence. Habit they said take time to form but very difficult to do way. This saying is linked to a student who is addicted to one form of lifestyles or the other like clubbing.

The findings from hypothesis onne indicated that, Federal and State Universities do not have any significant difference in the influence of peer pressure in relation to cultism, that both Federal and State Universities students were victims of peer pressure in relation to cultism. Peer pressure has great influence on one's decision making. This is because individual involved have access to each other every time especially in a learning environment. This findings is similar to the opinion of Inyang (2020) that, peer pressure influence students negatively irrespective of location. The findings is also inline with the finding of Adeniyi (2019), he found that, peer pressure have no statistically significant difference between different age groups on the combined dependent variables in the study area, that peer pressure influence students behaviour negatively.

The findings from hypotheses two indicated that, male and female students differ significantly in the influence of peer pressure on their behavioural patterns in relation to clubbing in University in North central Nigeria, that male students were more influenced. This findings is inline with the finding of Fadare, Zarma, Fadare, Bademosi and Amanum (2021) they found that, all the tested hypotheses were negative in relation to academic performance due to clubbing. This finding share similarity with other study because of the rate at which it had influence many students irrespective genders

The findings from hypotheses three revealed that, peer pressure had influence both Federal and State Universities students' academic achievement negatively. It has been said that social demands and peer pressure are powerful force influences one's choice and ultimately interrupt one's activities like studies. It is often believed that, anything that take one's time unconsciously can make a mark on a plan activities. Although, some students can perform better academically in the face of social peer pressure due to inherent tendency of an individual. This finding is similar to that of Fadare, Zarma, Fadare, Bademosi and Amanum (2021) they found that, all the tested hypotheses were negative in relation to academic performance due to clubbing.

CONCLUSION

From the findings of the study, some conclusion were made which are applicable to students in the Universities in North-central, Nigeria particularly Students in Federal and State Universities. It was concluded that, there were bad behavioural patterns as a result of peer pressure in the Universities in North central, Nigeria such as secret cult. It was also revealed that, the overall academic performance of students were within average. It was further concluded that, there were negative influence of peer

pressure in the area of addiction to clubbing. It was also concluded that, peer pressure influence both Federal and State Universities students' academic achievement negatively.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendation were made from the findings of this research;

1. Students' with bad behavioural patterns like secret cult should be encouraged to go for counselling. Parents, teachers, social organizations, religious bodies and all other stakeholders must also rise to the occasion by playing more positive roles in the upbringing of their children.
2. Parents, teachers and other stakeholders should always emphasize and educate the students on the importance of academic performance in relation to world of work.
3. Guidance counsellors, lecturer, religious leaders, social organization and other stakeholders should always use every available opportunity to educate students about the negative influence of peer pressure in relation to clubbing.

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